

Gamification Strategies for Enhancing Brand Loyalty: A Literature Review and Research Agenda

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Abstract: In today's highly competitive marketplace, building brand loyalty has become crucial for companies looking for sustainable success. A gamification is an innovative approach that applies game concepts to non-game situations and has drawn much attention as a potent tool to engage customers and strengthen brand loyalty. This article overviews the research on gamification tactics and how they affect building sustainable brand loyalty. The present study aimed to find out the gaps in the existing body of knowledge by consolidating existing works and identified that there is a contradiction between the researchers claiming the efficacy of gamification tactics and no proper remedies were suggested for overcoming the identified inefficiency of gamification strategies so that they might boost brand loyalty.

Keywords: Gamification; Brand Loyalty; Customer Engagement; Customer satisfaction; Customer attitude; Customer emotion; Customer Retention.

Introduction

Building a strong brand presence and encouraging client loyalty in the modern digital era have become critical goals for businesses looking to keep a competitive edge in the fast-paced and fiercely competitive corporate environment. For the past two decades, research on satisfaction has been acting as the "king" in marketing research (Oliver R L., 1999). As a result, numerous studies have been conducted on the different aspects of satisfaction (Szymanski and Henard, 2001) that can ultimately lead to customer loyalty (Chandrashekar *et al.*, 2007). Previous studies have confirmed that emotional value generates customer satisfaction, directly improving customer loyalty (Deng *et al.*, 2010).

Since both customer satisfaction and loyalty are part of the emotional outcome of the customer (Walsh *et al.*, 2011), it is essential to address the emotional aspects of the customer, and it must make sure that the customers are engaged with the brand.

For this purpose, various marketing techniques are used by different marketers. Among them, the most vibrant methods are gamification which is made possible by human-computer interaction.

Gamification has been a viable strategy to actively engage consumers, boost brand loyalty, and create long-lasting connections in recent years (Yang, Asaad and Dwivedi, 2017a; Xi and

Hamari, 2020). Even though the term gamification was initially developed in the digital media industry, its application and relevance in other areas are also growing rapidly (Kovačević, Zečević and Veljković, 2014) because of the tremendous technological changes and by utilizing this, anyone can create a 'process-related effect' that adopts positive relations, long-lasting engagement, and improved loyalty (Freudmann and Bakamitsos, 2014). The academicians show more interest in this area, and the number of papers published on gamification under different themes is growing rapidly (Hamari, Koivisto and Sarsa, 2014). Gamification adapts game principles to new contexts, enticing users to take advantage of features like prompt feedback and challenges while satisfying a variety of psychological demands via the fundamentals of game design (M. A. and Joy, 2022) and when compared to the majority of other digital marketing strategies, gamification has an unrivalled capacity to attract, stimulate, retain, and engage clients(Kuo and Chuang, 2016; Tiwari, 2023). Its fundamental objective is to elicit and reward customer feedback, which fosters engagement and fruitful relationship results and increases consumer loyalty and attachment(Harwood and Garry, 2015a).

In the present study, we are trying to synthesize current information, identify gaps, and suggest a research plan to increase understanding of this developing subject through a thorough literature review and an in-depth discussion of gamification tactics and how they could improve brand loyalty.

Gamification in digital marketing.

Businesses are continuously looking for novel methods to engage their customers and build long-lasting relationships in today's rapidly evolving digital environment because of the defunct marketing strategies that are no longer effective in attracting clients (M. A. and Joy, 2022). They are revolutionizing their processes and expanding unimaginable development potential via digitalization. This revolution is a part of introducing new marketing techniques by developing and incorporating games and gaming elements in the business environment, known as gamification (Rodrigues, Oliveira and Costa, 2016). By considering the definitions of gamification as per Table 1, we can conclude that; it is a process that incorporates game design aspects into non-game contexts to alter people's behaviour(Bunchball, 2010). By incorporating gamification into their digital marketing efforts, they can develop dynamic and engaging experiences that engage consumers, foster brand loyalty, and improve overall campaign performance (Xi and Hamari, 2020).

Table 1

1. Definitions of gamification

Definitions	Authors
“The use of game design elements in non-game contexts”.	(Deterding <i>et al.</i> , 2011)
“The process of game-thinking and game mechanics to engage users and solve problems.”	(Zichermann and Cunningham, 2011)
“Gamification uses game-based mechanics, aesthetics and game thinking to engage people, motivate action, promote learning, and solve	(Kapp, 2012)

problems.”	
“A process of enhancing a service with affordances for gameful experiences in order to support user's overall value creation.”	(Huotari and Hamari, 2012)
“The process of making activities more game-like”	(Werbach, 2014)
“The use of game design elements to enhance non-game goods and services by increasing customer value and encouraging value-creating behaviors such as increased consumption, greater loyalty, engagement, or product advocacy”	(Charles F. Hofacker <i>et al.</i> , 2016)
“Gamification enhances services through gameful experiences to support value creation.”	(Huotari and Hamari, 2017)

Making use of gaming elements in a non-gaming environment is done through gamification and creates a favorable emotion with the help of gamified platforms (Eppmann, Bekk and Klein, 2018); thus, it is considered the future of marketing as well as customer engagement (Zichermann and Cunningham, 2011). Studies found that the desire to interact with a gamified brand will likely result in a positive impression of the brand (Yang, Asaad and Dwivedi, 2017b). It also has a significant favorable influence on consumer experience and brand engagement (Jami Pour *et al.*, 2021). A reasonable consumer attitude may result from a gamified system's direct effect on several characteristics, including how valuable the system is seen to be, how easy it is to use, and how playfully it is used, as stated by (Lin *et al.*, 2020). According to (Adsit *et al.*, 1996), a positive attitude like this helps contribute to total customer satisfaction and develops customer loyalty among existing clients. According to (Zhong and Moon, 2020), as a direct result, clients who consistently show their loyalty are more likely to demonstrate an increased propensity to spend more money. (Hass *et al.*, 2021) also argue that consumers, especially young consumers, have a favorable attitude towards gamification until they get some reward, and it was confirmed by (Kirsch *et al.*, 2003; Wiltermuth, 2012) that reward is an element for motivation. Hence gamification is not a fad as it is likely to affect the customer experience (Charles F Hofacker *et al.*, 2016).

Digital Marketing and Brand Loyalty

“Brand loyalty is the commitment of consumers to consistently repurchase or consider a specific brand, rather than choosing from alternatives” (Oliver R L., 1999), or otherwise, the level of connection and commitment people have to a certain brand is known as brand loyalty (Han *et al.*, 2018) which is an essential component of consumer behavior. Brand loyalty in this article refers to customers' intense emotional attachment and unwavering commitment towards a certain brand, resulting in frequent engagement. Since brand loyalty develops a deep and strong emotional connection between consumers and a brand (Mckenzie *et al.*, 2020), It is one of the most crucial elements in establishing a brand's long-term achievement (Mellens, Dekimpe and Steenkamp, 1995; Amine, 1998). Companies may nurture brand loyalty and enjoy the advantages of repeat purchases, good word-of-mouth, and improved customer lifetime value if they create pleasant experiences for their customers, build trust

with their customers, and continually give importance to their customers (Gremler and Brown, 1999; Jonna and Stacey Menzel, 2001).

Building and maintaining brand loyalty has become a top priority as companies do business in today's highly competitive digital environment (Latif *et al.*, 2014; Tabaku and Zerellari, 2015), where consumers have a wide range of options. Effective gamification techniques for raising customer engagement are deeply ingrained in brand loyalty (Hwang and Choi, 2020). Gamification principles promote joy, which increases consumer engagement and boosts online shopping (Eisingerich *et al.*, 2019). accordingly, engaged customers tend to exhibit higher levels of loyalty due to their emotional investment and active involvement with the brand, fostered by personalized interactions and positive experiences that create a strong sense of trust and attachment towards the company (Hollebeek, 2011). In addition, organizations using gamified marketing techniques must design experiences that captivate users while achieving organizational objectives (Paharia, 2013). However, difficulties might occur when user motivations and corporate objectives are not entirely aligned (Callan, Bauer and Landers, 2015); if user motivations and organizational goals are not as expected, it can result in an ineffective experience and damages users' already-existing interest and engagement (Rigby and Ryan, 2011; Muntasir *et al.*, 2015). Moreover, the conclusion of the study conducted by (Harwood & Garry, 2015) says there is insufficient evidence to support the possibility of achieving the high-quality engagement outcomes that are suggested in their model, even though gamified experience environment attempts to gain positive relational outcomes like loyalty and relationship development by emulating gameplay engagement and triggering and incentivizing customer responses.

However, Gamification promotes a stronger emotional connection between customers and businesses by inciting and rewarding customer behaviors similar to videogame participation (Yang, Asaad and Dwivedi, 2017b). Customers engage more in a company when they actively participate in gamified interactions, which leads to repeat business, good word-of-mouth, and increased customer lifetime value (Eisingerich *et al.*, 2019; Bauer *et al.*, 2020). The gamified interactions foster a feeling of authenticity, trust, and tailored connections that appeal to customers in the digital age(Hosseini and Rezvani, 2021). Knowing how gamification and brand loyalty work together may help marketers create creative campaigns that engage audiences, foster lasting loyalty, and help their companies succeed in the fast-paced, competitive marketplace.

Perils of gamification

Even though the gamified system is supported and welcomed by most researchers, in contradiction, some researchers are pointing their studies towards the negative effect of gamification (de Jesus *et al.*, 2019). Even if an insignificant number of researchers support it, we must address gamification's adverse impact or ineffectiveness while designing a gamified system. Researchers argue that loss or failure in the game may create negative customer Behaviour and thus affect the business adversely (Leclercq, Hammedi and Poncin, 2018a). Customers continue to acquire negative impressions and behave negatively toward the company when they have a failure or bad experience (Baker and Kim, 2018). Gamification is seen as ethical by customers as long as they have a choice to participate voluntarily (Hass, Hass and Joseph, 2021a). Once the gamification becomes compulsory, it creates a severe negative attitude towards the gamifying system. Negative behaviors will also make when the

customer comes across any undesirable experience due to the system's failure in the past (Wallin, 1999); in such cases, gamification may not be effective. (2013) argue that even if the customers win the challenges or other conditions, their mood will influence that particular moment. Thus the gamified system becomes a failure. Hence the companies should consider the moderation factors while designing the system. (Srivastava *et al.*, 2022) found five elements that negatively impact the mental and emotional well-being of customers engaged with gamified systems. "Privacy invasion", "exhaustion", "gamification addiction", "cyber aggression", and "cyberbullying" are the elements that have been mentioned as being a component of gamification's dark side. Likewise, (Okeet *et al.*, 2023) also identified significant obstacles to the adoption of gamification, such as "lack of capacity and "expertise", "lack of budgeting for innovation", "lack of technical infrastructure", "hesitation to adopt and limited internet connectivity" moreover he classified the issues into five main groups, including "organizational challenges", "technical-related challenges", "human-related challenges", "data security challenges", and "economic challenges".

Discussion

The studies show that gamification strategies, when effectively implemented, positively impact brand loyalty among consumers (Freudmann and Bakamitsos, 2014; Xi and Hamari, 2020). Furthermore, studies have also proven that incorporating game elements, such as rewards, challenges, and badges, can increase customer engagement with the brand (Hass, Hass and Joseph, 2021b). Moreover, a positive attitude towards a brand contributes to overall customer satisfaction through which customer loyalty is created, and thus they tempt to spend more (Adsit *et al.*, 1996; Zhong and Moon, 2020). All these findings conclude that gamification is effective in creating brand loyalty. In the case of the relationship between gamification and customer retention, various studies examined the correlation between gamification initiatives and improved customer retention rates and found significantly positive (Kuo and Chuang, 2016; Behl *et al.*, 2020; Ruengaramrut, Ribiere and Mariano, 2020; Tiwari, 2023). Gamified loyalty programs increase repeat purchases and decrease customer churn (Sharp and Sharp, 1997; Meyer-Waarden and Benavent, 2006).

Past research uncovered the impact of Gamification on Customer Engagement Researches shows that gamification contributes to increased customer engagement with the brand significantly improved(Zichermann and Cunningham, 2011; Yang, Asaad and Dwivedi, 2017a; Bauer *et al.*, 2020; Hwang and Choi, 2020; Xi and Hamari, 2020). Customer perceptions of gamified loyalty programs were addressed by many researchers and found delves into consumer perceptions of gamified loyalty programs, examining attitudes, motivations, and potential barriers to participation (Sharp and Sharp, 1997; Meyer-Waarden, 2005; Tabaku and Zerellari, 2015). Research on gamification and emotional connection with the brand explored how gamification elements contribute to building emotional relationships between customers and the brand (Hollebeek, 2011; Eppmann, Bekk and Klein, 2018; Hosseini and Rezvani, 2021).

Even though decidedly gamification has so many advantages in the marketing context and has been well explored, it is not free from disadvantages (Hyrynsalmi, Smed and Kimppa, 2017). The potential challenges and risks of gamification were not that much explored, but still some of the studies done by (Leclercq, Hammedi and Poncin, 2018b; de Jesus *et al.*, 2019; Hass, Hass and Joseph, 2021b; Okeet *et al.*, 2023) discuss potential drawbacks and risks

associated with gamification, such as customer fatigue, unintended consequences, or ethical considerations etc.,

Conceptual Model

Conclusion and Future Research Directions

Scholars and experts have debated whether gamification is good. According to academics and industry experts, gamification may boost customer engagement and brand loyalty. These scholars and industry people cite gamification's effective use and positive effects. However, other experts challenge gamification's efficacy, especially when it's poorly designed or doesn't provide actual rewards. Gamification's impact depends on the venue, audience, and execution; they say that even though gamification has limitations, as per the currently available evidence, only an insignificant number of limitations can be pointed out. However, it is a novel marketing method that has several advantages. Future researchers should focus on this contradiction and how these issues can be eliminated. This study was not systematically conducted. Hence, the data selection may be biased, so future researchers can focus on this limitation and explore this gap by conducting a systematic review.

In conclusion, this literature review on gamification strategies for brand loyalty offers insights into their potential benefits and drawbacks. The findings suggest that well-designed and executed gamification boosts customer loyalty, and engagement and retention can be achieved. However, unique traits, business-specific aspects, and long-term gamification project feasibility must be considered. This study lays the groundwork for future research into specific gamification techniques, customer perceptions, and the ethical implications of gamification strategies, which will help marketers and researchers implement gamification more effectively and responsibly to build brand loyalty.

References

Adsit, D.J. *et al.* (1996) 'Relationships between employee attitudes, customer satisfaction and departmental performance', *Journal of Management Development*, 15(1), pp. 62–75. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/02621719610107827>.

- Amine, A. (1998) 'Consumer s' true brand loyalty: The central role of commitment', *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 6(4), pp. 305–319. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/096525498346577>.
- Baker, M.A. and Kim, K. (2018) 'Other Customer Service Failures: Emotions, Impacts, and Attributions', *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Research*, 42(7), pp. 1067–1085. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1096348016671394>.
- Bauer, J.C. *et al.* (2020) 'Gamifying the digital shopping experience: games without monetary participation incentives increase customer satisfaction and loyalty', *Journal of Service Management*, 31(3), pp. 563–595. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JOSM-10-2018-0347>.
- Behl, A. *et al.* (2020) 'Gamification in e-commerce: A comprehensive review of literature', *Journal of Electronic Commerce in Organizations*, 18(2), pp. 1–16. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4018/JECO.2020040101>.
- Bunchball (2010) 'Gamification 101: An Introduction to the Use of Game', (October). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2012.12.020>.
- Callan, R.C., Bauer, K.N. and Landers, R.N. (2015) 'How to Avoid the Dark Side of Gamification: Ten Business Scenarios and Their Unintended Consequences', in T. Reiners and L.C. Wood (eds) *Gamification in Education and Business*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 553–568. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-10208-5_28.
- Chandrashekar, M. *et al.* (2007) 'Satisfaction strength and customer loyalty', *Journal of Marketing Research*, 44(1), pp. 153–163. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkr.44.1.153>.
- Deng, Z. *et al.* (2010) 'Understanding customer satisfaction and loyalty: An empirical study of mobile instant messages in China', *International Journal of Information Management*, 30(4), pp. 289–300. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2009.10.001>.
- Deterding, S. *et al.* (2011) 'From Game Design Elements to Gamefulness: Defining "Gamification"', *Proceedings of the 15th International Academic MindTrek Conference: Envisioning Future Media Environments, MindTrek 2011*, pp. 9–15.
- Eisingerich, A.B. *et al.* (2019) 'Hook vs. hope: How to enhance customer engagement through gamification', *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 36(2), pp. 200–215. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijresmar.2019.02.003>.
- Eppmann, R., Bekk, M. and Klein, K. (2018) 'Gameful Experience in Gamification: Construction and Validation of a Gameful Experience Scale [GAMEX]', *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 43(2018), pp. 98–115. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intmar.2018.03.002>.
- Freudmann, E.A. and Bakamitsos, Y. (2014) 'The Role of Gamification in Non-profit Marketing: An Information Processing Account.', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 148, pp. 567–572. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.07.081>.
- Gremler, D.D. and Brown, S.W. (1999) 'The loyalty ripple effect: Appreciating the full value of customers', *International Journal of Service Industry Management*, 10(3), pp. 271–291. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/09564239910276872>.

- Hamari, J., Koivisto, J. and Sarsa, H. (2014) ‘Does gamification work? - A literature review of empirical studies on gamification’, in *Proceedings of the Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*. IEEE Computer Society, pp. 3025–3034. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/HICSS.2014.377>.
- Han, H. *et al.* (2018) ‘Drivers of brand loyalty in the chain coffee shop industry’, *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 72(November 2017), pp. 86–97. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2017.12.011>.
- Harwood, T. and Garry, T. (2015a) ‘An investigation into gamification as a customer engagement experience environment’, *Journal of Services Marketing*, 29(6–7), pp. 533–546. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSM-01-2015-0045>.
- Harwood, T. and Garry, T. (2015b) ‘An investigation into gamification as a customer engagement experience environment’, *Journal of Services Marketing*, 29(6–7), pp. 533–546. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSM-01-2015-0045>.
- Hass, D., Hass, A. and Joseph, M. (2021a) ‘A preliminary investigation of gamification from the young consumer’s perspective’, *Young Consumers*, 22(3), pp. 413–428. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/YC-10-2020-1221>.
- Hass, D., Hass, A. and Joseph, M. (2021b) ‘A preliminary investigation of gamification from the young consumer’s perspective’, *Young Consumers*, 22(3), pp. 413–428. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/YC-10-2020-1221>.
- Hofacker, Charles F. *et al.* (2016) ‘Gamification and Mobile Marketing Effectiveness’, *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 34, pp. 25–36. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intmar.2016.03.001>.
- Hofacker, Charles F. *et al.* (2016) ‘Gamification and Mobile Marketing Effectiveness’, *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 34, pp. 25–36.
- Hollebeek, L.D. (2011) ‘Demystifying customer brand engagement: Exploring the loyalty nexus’, *Journal of Marketing Management*, 27(7–8), pp. 785–807. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/0267257X.2010.500132>.
- Hosseini, E. and Rezvani, M.H. (2021) ‘E-customer loyalty in gamified trusted store platforms: A case study analysis in Iran’, *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, 10(5), pp. 2899–2909. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.11591/eei.v10i5.3165>.
- Huotari, K. and Hamari, J. (2012) ‘Defining gamification - A service marketing perspective’, *Proceedings of the 16th International Academic MindTrek Conference 2012: ‘Envisioning Future Media Environments’*, *MindTrek 2012*, pp. 17–22. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1145/2393132.2393137>.
- Huotari, K. and Hamari, J. (2017) ‘A definition for gamification: anchoring gamification in the service marketing literature’, *Electronic Markets*, 27(1), pp. 21–31. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12525-015-0212-z>.
- Hwang, J. and Choi, L. (2020) ‘Having fun while receiving rewards?: Exploration of gamification in loyalty programs for consumer loyalty’, *Journal of Business Research*,

- 106(November 2017), pp. 365–376. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.01.031>.
- Hyrnsalmi, S., Smed, J. and Kimppa, K.K. (2017) ‘The dark side of gamification: How we should stop worrying and study also the negative impacts of bringing game design elements to everywhere’, *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*, 1857, pp. 96–104.
- Jami Pour, M. *et al.* (2021) ‘Gamification and customer experience: the mediating role of brand engagement in online grocery retailing’, *Nankai Business Review International*, 12(3), pp. 340–357. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/NBRI-07-2020-0041>.
- de Jesus, G.M. *et al.* (2019) ‘Is it worth using gamification on software testing education? An experience report’, *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3364641.3364661>.
- Jonna, H. and Stacey Menzel, B. (2001) ‘Customer participation in creating site brand loyalty’, *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 15(4), pp. 34–45.
- Kapp, K.M. (2012) *The Gamification Instruction of Learning and Game-Based Methods and Strategies for Training and Education*.
- Kirsch, P. *et al.* (2003) ‘Anticipation of reward in a nonaversive differential conditioning paradigm and the brain reward system: An event-related fMRI study’, *NeuroImage*, 20(2), pp. 1086–1095. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1053-8119\(03\)00381-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1053-8119(03)00381-1).
- Kovačević, I., Zečević, B. and Veljković, S. (2014) ‘“Gamification” concept: Theoretical framework and destination marketing management practice’.
- Kuo, M.S. and Chuang, T.Y. (2016) ‘How gamification motivates visits and engagement for online academic dissemination - An empirical study’, *Computers in Human Behavior*, 55, pp. 16–27. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.08.025>.
- Latif, W.B. *et al.* (2014) ‘A CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK TO BUILD BRAND LOYALTY IN THE MODERN MARKETING ENVIRONMENT Contribution/ Originality’, *Journal of Asian Scientific Research*, 4(410), pp. 547–557.
- Leclercq, T., Hammedi, W. and Poncin, I. (2018a) ‘The Boundaries of Gamification for Engaging Customers: Effects of Losing a Contest in Online Co-creation Communities’, *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 44, pp. 82–101. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intmar.2018.04.004>.
- Leclercq, T., Hammedi, W. and Poncin, I. (2018b) ‘The Boundaries of Gamification for Engaging Customers: Effects of Losing a Contest in Online Co-creation Communities’, *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 44, pp. 82–101. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intmar.2018.04.004>.
- Lin, C.W. *et al.* (2020) ‘Exploring the Adoption of Nike+ Run Club App: An Application of the Theory of Reasoned Action’, *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2020. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/8568629>.
- M. A., E.J. and Joy, M.M. (2022) ‘Application of Gamification in a Marketing Context’, in, pp. 121–136. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-9223-6.ch006>.

- Mckenzie, R. *et al.* (2020) ‘THE VALUE OF LOYALTY : UNDERSTANDING BRAND LOYALTY FROM A CONSUMER’, 11(1), pp. 1–8.
- Mellens, M., Dekimpe, M. and Steenkamp, J. (1995) ‘A review of brand-loyalty measures in marketing’, *DTEW Research Report 9516*, XLI(2), pp. 1–27.
- Meyer-Waarden, L. (2005) ‘Loyalty Programs and Their Impact on Repeat Purchase Behaviour: An Extension on the “Single Source” Panel BehaviorScan’, *Data Analysis and Decision Support*, pp. 257–268. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-28397-8_29.
- Meyer-Waarden, L. and Benavent, C. (2006) ‘The Impact of Loyalty Programmes on Repeat Purchase Behaviour’, *Journal of Marketing Management*, 22(1–2), pp. 61–88. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1362/026725706776022308>.
- Muntasir, M. *et al.* (2015) ‘The gamification of medical education: a broader perspective’, *Medical Education Online*, 20(1), pp. 18–20. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3402/MEO.V20.30566>.
- Oke, A.E. *et al.* (2023) ‘Application of gamification for sustainable construction: an evaluation of the challenges’, *Construction Innovation*, ahead-of-p(ahead-of-print). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/CI-09-2022-0247>.
- Oliver R L. (1999) ‘Whence consumer loyalty?’, *Journal of Marketing*, 63, p. 33.
- Paharia, R. (2013) *Loyalty 3.0: How to Revolutionize Customer and Employee Engagement with Big Data and Gamification*. <country>US</country>: McGraw-Hill. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1036/9780071813389>.
- Rigby, S. and Ryan, R.M. (2011) *GLUED TO GAMES: How Video Games Draw Us In and Hold Us Spellbound*, *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, 6(11), 951–952.
- Rodrigues, L.F., Oliveira, A. and Costa, C.J. (2016) ‘Playing seriously - How gamification and social cues influence bank customers to use gamified e-business applications’, *Computers in Human Behavior*, 63, pp. 392–407. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2016.05.063>.
- Ruengaramrut, V., Ribiere, V. and Mariano, S. (2020) ‘The moderating effect of gamification on the relationship between customer engagement and new service development process involvement’, *International Journal of Innovation and Learning*, 27(1), pp. 93–119. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJIL.2020.103895>.
- Sharp, B. and Sharp, A. (1997) ‘Loyalty programs and their impact on repeat-purchase loyalty patterns’, *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 14(5), pp. 473–486. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0167-8116\(97\)00022-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0167-8116(97)00022-0).
- Srivastava, G. *et al.* (2022) ‘Examining the dark side of using gamification elements in online community engagement: an application of PLS-SEM and ANN modeling’, *Benchmarking [Preprint]*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-03-2022-0160>.
- Szymanski, D.M. and Henard, D.H. (2001) ‘Customer satisfaction: A meta-analysis of the empirical evidence’, *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 29(1), pp. 16–35. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/009207030102900102>.

- Tabaku, E. and Zerellari, M. (Mersini)** (2015) ‘Brand Loyalty and Loyalty Programs’, *Romanian Economic and Business Review*, 10(2), pp. 71–86.
- Tiwari, A. (2023) ‘Gamification Can Help Improve your Marketing Mix’, *Business World*, March, pp. 22–23.
- Wallin, T. (1999) ‘What Drives Customer Loyalty With Complaint Resolution?’, (4), pp. 324–332.
- Walsh, G. *et al.* (2011) ‘Emotions, store-environmental cues, store-choice criteria, and marketing outcomes’, *Journal of Business Research*, 64(7), pp. 737–744. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2010.07.008>.
- Werbach, K. (2014) ‘(Re) Defining gamification: a process approach, persuasive technology’, *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, 8462, pp. 266–272.
- Wiltermuth, S. (2012) “‘I’ll Have One of Each’’: How Separating Rewards into (Meaningless) Categories Increases Motivation’, *Academy of Management Proceedings*, 2012(1), p. 10972. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5465/ambpp.2012.10972abstract>.
- Xi, N. and Hamari, J. (2020) ‘Does gamification affect brand engagement and equity? A study in online brand communities’, *Journal of Business Research*, 109(November 2019), pp. 449–460. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.11.058>.
- Yang, Y., Asaad, Y. and Dwivedi, Y. (2017a) ‘Examining the impact of gamification on intention of engagement and brand attitude in the marketing context’, *Computers in Human Behavior*, 73, pp. 459–469. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2017.03.066>.
- Yang, Y., Asaad, Y. and Dwivedi, Y. (2017b) ‘Examining the impact of gamification on intention of engagement and brand attitude in the marketing context’, *Computers in Human Behavior*, 73, pp. 459–469. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2017.03.066>.
- Zhong, Y. and Moon, H.C. (2020) ‘What Drives Customer Satisfaction, Loyalty, and Happiness in Fast-Food Restaurants in China? Perceived Price, Service Quality, Food Quality, Physical Environment Quality, and the Moderating Role of Gender’, *foods*, MDPI, 9(4), pp. 1–16.
- Zichermann, G. and Cunningham, C. (2011) *ZICHERMANN, G.; CUNNINGHAM, C. Gamification by design: Implementing game mechanics in web and mobile apps. O’Reilly Media, 2011, O’Reilly Media, Inc.*